

Deliverable 3.7

Technical report on information extraction from heterogeneous data using TDM

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Abstract:

This deliverable is a technical report on information extraction from heterogeneous data using TDM. It consists of the overview of the achieved results for the various topics investigated under the umbrella of SSHOC Task 3.3: keyword extraction from multilingual texts, including legal texts in multiple languages; linguistic analysis for semantic annotation of social phenomena on the example of verbal aggression; annotation and processing of historical texts. Resulting pipelines are published via SSHOC Marketplace, in the form of workflows pointing to data processing scripts and services.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the activities within Task 3.3. that were led by CLARIN ERIC with the main partners CLARIN/Athena, CLARIN/CUNI, and DARIAH/UGOE, and additional collaboration with SciencesPo. Over the course of M1-M38 the partners developed three demonstration scenarios that highlight the value of NLP (Natural Language Processing) technologies for the SSH field and investigated which aspects of the outcomes of T3.3. and in which form can be shared via SSH Open Marketplace.

Three types of scenarios include: (1) Application of TDM (Text Data Mining) to large bodies of multilingual texts on the use case of processing Collective Bargaining Agreements (CBAs); (2) Integration of linguistic analysis for information extraction into SSH tasks on the use case of verbal aggression detection in the context of social media. (3) TDM handling of heterogeneous data on the use case of processing the intertextuality phenomena in European drama history.

All use cases work with data in multiple languages, and created pipelines take this multilinguality into account.

The outcome of the demonstrations are stored to be accessed after the end of the project as online code notebooks and a workflow on SSH Open Marketplace (use case 1¹), service in the EOSC portal (use case 2²), and a set of python scripts on the publicly accessible GitHub pages and a workflow on SSH Open Marketplace (use case 3³).

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CBA	Collective Bargaining Agreement
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FTS	Finite State Transducers
ILO	International Labour Organisation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POS	Part of speech
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TDM	Text and Data Mining
TF-IDF	Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency
TG	Target of attack
VA	Verbal Aggression
VAM	Verbally aggressive message

¹ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/iRDSS0>

² <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/verbal-aggression-analyser-va-analyser>

³ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/DMJlZG>

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1. Introduction

The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC) aims at providing a cloud infrastructure where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for social sciences and humanities (SSH) users. The goal is to create a cloud ecosystem through the design, development, and maintenance of user-friendly tools and services, covering all aspects of the SSH research data lifecycle. These tools and services are made accessible via SSH Open Marketplace that has been created in the context of the project⁴. One of the ways to attract potential users from the field is to showcase how those tools and services could be used in practice to address the challenges that are similar to the ones they work with in their respective fields. In this way the usefulness of text and data mining (TDM) in the context of SSH is demonstrated for three particular use cases that highlight diversity of approaches, data processing methods, and ways to share the output with the broader audience.

2. Use of TDM in the context of various SSH tasks

2.1 Application of TDM to large bodies of multilingual texts. Use case: Collective Bargaining Agreements (CBAs)

2.1.1 Definition of the task

When independent unions and employers (or employers' organisations) negotiate terms and conditions of employment and regulate relations between the parties, this activity is referred to as 'collective bargaining' (ILO Convention 154⁵). The written document resulting from this negotiation is a legal document, called collective bargaining agreement (CBA).

While the importance of CBAs is agreed upon at global level, only a few countries in the world keep a database of the provisions agreed in these agreements. And even in those cases – e.g., in the UK, New Zealand, Brazil, Italy – the databases are not comparable across countries.

Since 2012, the WageIndicator Foundation has been collecting and annotating CBAs on a global scale in the WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database⁶, which now contains 1668 CBAs in 27 different

⁴ SSHOC Deliverable D7.1. https://zenodo.org/record/4558302#_YkSFeC8RppQ

⁵ ILO Convention 154:

https://www.ilo.org/dyn/normlex/en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_INSTRUMENT_ID:312299

⁶ WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database: <https://wageindicator.org/cbadatabase>

languages and coming from 61 countries. For each and every CBA, the WageIndicator team answers a series of questions related to several topics and annotates the agreements.

One of the main challenges of this process is the manual annotation (in terms of working hours/effort) in the annotation system of WageIndicator, which is called Cobra⁷, where - for each and every CBA - the team answers to a series of questions related to twelve topics: General CBA data, Job titles, Social security and pensions, Training, Employment contracts, Sickness and disability, Health and medical assistance, Work/family balance arrangements, Gender equality issues, Wages, Working hours and Coverage. The coding process of collective agreements is a time-consuming activity. When answering a question, e.g. *How long is the trial period for a manual skilled worker in DAYS (including renewal)?*, the annotator often looks for words which usually are contained in the section where the topic - here: trial or probation period - is addressed. For example, he/she might look for the terms such as 'trial' or 'probation' to see if something comes out. This does not always work, as in reality in many cases there are more terms which could help to find a relevant section but the annotator might not be aware of them. WageIndicator tested this by creating a simple vocabulary for the most common languages in the database (English, Spanish, Italian and French). The vocabulary was based on what were assumed to be the most common words for a topic, but this worked only for the most specific topics (e.g. 'maternity leave') but not for most of them, partly because words can come in different forms, partly because legal texts sometimes have a specific vocabulary which might be different from the common language, partly because some words are common in more topics, so they don't help in finding the right paragraphs. One successful case has been Spanish, but the annotator who worked on this vocabulary has a long experience in collective agreements from Spanish-speaking countries, speaks perfect Spanish and spent a couple of years refining his vocabulary. These conditions are very hard to replicate for all other languages. This challenging situation becomes harder to deal with when the agreement is not written in the annotator's mother tongue and there is nobody in the team who speaks the language.

Multilinguality is the second big challenge here: the collective agreements contained in the database are written in 27 different languages, and when an additional country is included, this often equals the addition of a new language to the collection, and it cannot be planned in advance to have access to trained annotators who would be native speakers of all these languages.

Based on this experience and given the two main challenges, an initial hypothesis has been that the identification of a simple keywords list could serve as a possible solution to speed up the coding process. Such a script was created to find the keywords based on simple words' frequency. However, when the terms from the keywords list were highlighted in new collective agreements, they were too many and not specific enough to carry out the task in an efficient way, and therefore, it was not of help for the annotators to spot the right piece of text.

Thus, the tasks identified to be carried out under the umbrella of SSHOC project are:

1. Enhance and widen the quantity of data, i.e. increase the number of collective agreements in the system to make the overall dataset more representative and robust to underlying linguistic variability, with more CBAs for more common languages, such as Spanish, French and

⁷ Manual and Codebook of the Cobra System: [Ceccon, D., & Medas, G. \(2021\). Codebook WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database – Version 4 – January 2021. WageIndicator Foundation, Amsterdam](#); [date of access - 17.11.2021.];

Portuguese, and more CBAs for languages that currently have only a few, such as Turkish, German, Romanian, Swedish.

2. Improve and accelerate the searching of the data, i.e. use machine learning techniques to identify where in a CBA a specific topic is addressed, so that annotators would not need to go through the full text many times, but could just search for the information of interest in a limited portion of text. This would reduce the time needed to annotate and analyse agreements and enable faster and more accurate identification of the relevant clauses. Also, such a tool would be very useful for anyone who wants to extract information about the content of new collective agreements or possibly other labour-related legal texts.

2.1.2 Dataset description

The CBA texts can come in different formats, such as Word, readable PDF, scanned PDF, scanned JPG, paper. The first step for the annotator is always to make a Word version of it, sometimes through an OCR text recognition software (Abby FineReader is currently being used for this). Afterwards, the text is transformed into html and three levels of titles are assigned to structure it. This is necessary to be able to identify the boundaries of one segment of text (clause) at a later stage. Any html editor can be used for this operation: currently the team is using Amaya⁸ or Bluefish Editor⁹ (both open-source). After assigning H1 to the title, H2 to the chapters/parts and H3 to the articles of the agreement, the html is then uploaded to the annotation system of WageIndicator (Cobra). The database's coding scheme consists of 619 variables in total. Figure 1 shows the first questions in section Employment contracts, which starts with a trigger question. If the answer to the trigger question is Yes, then more relevant questions pop up.

Figure 1. Example of trigger question and follow-up question in Cobra annotation system

⁸ Amaya web editor: <https://www.w3.org/Amaya/>

⁹ BlueFish editor: <https://bluefish.openoffice.nl/index.html>

For each question, the appropriate piece of text – the so-called ‘clause’ - is found and stored in the database in a process also known as “text annotation”. Figure 2 shows an example of a question where a piece of text was selected:

Figure 2. Example of question with selected clause in Cobra annotation system

Figure 3 shows how the selected clause looks in the text:

Figure 3. Example of selected clause in Cobra annotation system

This process produces two datasets: one includes the data resulting from the coding, the other collects the clauses selected for each variable. A dataset with all the html CBA texts used is also available. For task 2 mentioned in 2.1.1, the full texts dataset and the clauses dataset have been used. Both are available in Zenodo¹⁰.

The clauses dataset (WageIndicator_CBADatabase_Selected_Clauses_211019.csv) is composed of the following seven variables:

- *cba_id* – it’s the id of the collective agreement in Cobra (e.g. *collective-agreement-between-better-best-academy-and-union-of-education-agriculture-general-service-workers*);
- *country* (e.g. *ghana*);
- *countrycode* – it’s the ISO 3166-1 numeric code of the country (e.g. 288 for Ghana);
- *locale* – it includes a two-letter language code and a two-letter country code (e.g. *EN_GH* for Ghana)
- *bind* – it’s the id of the question asked in the coding (e.g. *contracttrialperiod*);

¹⁰ Daniela Ceccon, & Gabriele Medas. (2021). WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database Dataset with Full Texts and Selected Clauses [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5651624>

- *label* – it's the question asked in the coding in natural language (e.g. *How long is the trial period for a manual skilled worker in DAYS (including renewal)?*);
- *clause* – it's the clause selected by the annotator when answering the question (e.g. *i.The employer shall subject newly engaged workers to a minimum of three months and maximum of six months' probation during which period the employee shall be carefully observed regarding his/her suitability for the assigned job.*).

The full texts dataset (WageIndicator_CBADatabase_Full_Texts_211019.csv) is composed of the following five variables:

- *cba_id* – it's the id of the collective agreement in Cobra (e.g. *collective-agreement-between-better-best-academy-and-union-of-education-agriculture-general-s ervice-workers*);
- *country* (e.g. *ghana*);
- *countrycode* – it's the ISO 3166-1 numeric code of the country (e.g. *288* for Ghana);
- *locale* – it includes a two-letter language code and a two-letter country code (e.g. *EN_GH* for Ghana)
- *text* – it's the full text of the collective agreement in html format.

An online script in the form of a guided notebook has been created in Google Colaboratory¹¹. This guided notebook is connected to Zenodo, where the datasets are stored, but it can work on any machine and is available in the SSHOC Marketplace¹².

In the notebook, the following steps are taken:

- Load libraries and setup access: To work with the two datasets, and to create and test machine learning models, some specific libraries and modules need to be imported. Also, Pickle libraries and functions are needed for saving and loading objects from Google Drive. The explanation of what each of the libraries/modules does is provided within the code. This step has to be taken only once: once that is done, it is possible to continue working without having to upload the datasets every time;
- Load raw data (can be skipped if loading pre-saved data): The two datasets are stored in Zenodo and need to be retrieved and saved as dataframes;
- Process data (can be skipped if loading pre-saved data). Steps:
 - a) Extracts the language from the locale (by taking the first 2 characters) and creates a new variable called *language*
 - b) Creates a set that has a unique list of all languages, called *languages* and includes each language as a dictionary in the paragraphs dictionary.
 - c) For each language, creates a new set that has a unique list of texts in that language, called *xmls*.
 - d) Parses each of these texts in paragraphs and creates a list of paragraphs for each xml called *xml_paragraphs* and includes each paragraph in the language within the paragraphs dictionary (example in Figure 4, showing the first 10 paragraphs for Italian):

¹¹ <https://colab.research.google.com/>

¹² <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/iRDSS0>

```
dict_keys(['CS', 'NL', 'PL', 'BN', 'DA', 'ET', 'TR', 'HR', 'AM', 'SL', 'HU', 'RO', 'BA', 'FI', 'KM', 'SV', 'ES', 'PT', 'MT',
'VI', 'IT', 'EN', 'BG', 'FR', 'SR', 'SK', 'EL', 'LT', 'DE'])
{'': [],
 'Il giorno 29 gennaio 2019, presso la sede di Roma dell'Agencia nazionale nper l'attrazione degli investimenti e lo sviluppo
 d'impresa - INVITALIA\n- , si sono incontrati:': [],
 'Roma, 29 gennaio 2019': [],
 'Valido dal 1° gennaio 2017 al 31 dicembre 2019': [],
 'e le OO.SS della stessa:': [],
 'l'Agencia nazionale per l'attrazione degli investimenti e lo sviluppo\nd'impresa rappresentata da:': [],
 '•Antonio Migliardi': [],
 '•Gabriella Forte': [],
 '•Giuseppe Galati': [],
 '•Renato Gemma': []}]
```

Figure 4. Example of text parsing into paragraphs for the Italian language

- e) Creates a list of all languages. For each language, creates a new set that has a unique list of binds in that language, called *binds*.
- f) For each bind and language, creates a new set that has a unique list of clauses in that language and bind called *clauses_of_bind* (Figure 5 shows the number of clauses identified for some binds in Czech)

```
'LANGUAGE: CS'
'BIND: HARDSHIP_trigger'
'Clauses :6'
'BIND: standbyallowancepercl'
'Clauses :1'
'BIND: SUNDAY_trigger'
'Clauses :6'
'BIND: healthandsafetytrainingtxt'
'Clauses :1'
'BIND: JOBTYPES_comments_txt'
'Clauses :1'
'BIND: OVERTIME_trigger'
'Clauses :6'
```

Figure 5. Example showing the number of clauses identified for some binds in the Czech language

- g) For each clause, creates a new set that has a unique list of paragraphs that contain that clause called *paragraphs_with_clause*.
- h) For each paragraph with a clause, if the bind is not already associated with that paragraph, it's appended to it.
- i) Retrieves the paragraphs from the dictionary and creates a dataframe per language called *all_binds_languages* with a binary variable for each bind, identifying whether the clause is assigned to that paragraph or not: 1 is assigned when the paragraph is associated with a bind, and a 0 when it is not. Figure 6 shows an example for German:

	par	paidpaternityleavetxt	HARDSHIP_trigger	SUNDAY_trigger	paidpaternityleaveduration
0	Arb./Ang. Mürztaler Verkehrs- GmbH / Rahmen - 01.01.2015	0	0	0	0
1	Stichtag: 28.07.2020	0	0	0	0
2	*****	0	0	0	0
3	MÜRZTALER VERKEHRS- GMBH / RAHMEN	0	0	0	0
4	gültig ab 1. Jänner 2015	0	0	0	0

Figure 6. Example of binary variables assigned to paragraphs for some binds in the German language

- j) As different thresholds for number of paragraphs found per bind have been tested and 5 was empirically found to be the best threshold to ensure enough training data is available for the models, the 1s and 0s are summed for each bind and only the binds that have at least 5 paragraphs are included in the training.
- k) Performs cleaning of the paragraphs. The tools used for lemmatization are WordNet stemmer¹³ for English, SnowballStemmer¹⁴ for other languages and Stopwords to remove stop words. The lemmatization of each clause includes the following actions: removes double whitespaces, tokenizes, filters out all non-alphabetic and non-numeric characters, lemmatizes or stems, removes stopwords, replaces numbers with strings, removes one- and two-letter words.
- l) Saves the cleaned paragraphs as *cleaned_par* in *all_binds_languages*. Figure 7 shows an example for Italian:

	par	cleaned_par
0		
1	Valido dal 1° gennaio 2017 al 31 dicembre 2019	valid gennai <numeric> <numeric> dicembr <numeric>
2	Roma, 29 gennaio 2019	rom <numeric> gennai <numeric>
3	Il giorno 29 gennaio 2019, presso la sede di Roma dell'Agenzia nazionale per l'attrazione degli investimenti e lo sviluppo d'impresa – INVITALIA...	giorn <numeric> gennai <numeric> press sed rom agenz nazional attrazion invest svilupp impres invital son incontr
4	l'Agenzia nazionale per l'attrazione degli investimenti e lo sviluppo d'impresa rappresentata da:	agenz nazional attrazion invest svilupp impres rappresent
5	•Antonio Migliardi	migliard
6	•Giuseppe Galati	gal
7	•Gabiella Forte	fort
8	•Renato Gemma	gemma
9	e le OO.SS della stessa:	stess

Figure 7. Example of paragraphs and cleaned paragraphs in the Italian language

¹³ NLTK Project (2019), [Natural Language Toolkit: WordNet stemmer interface](#)

¹⁴ NLTK Project (2019), [Natural Language Toolkit: Snowball Stemmer](#)

m) The file *all_binds_languages* is saved in Google Drive and can be retrieved any time as pre-saved processed data when running the script as this is the dataset on which machine learning techniques are applied.

- Load pre-saved processed data
- Relative Frequency model: creates the function for training and testing the Relative Frequency model. Steps:

1. TRAINING

- a) For each bind, it creates a string with paragraphs in the train group that have the bind, and one with the words' frequency in that group.
- b) For each bind, it creates a variable with paragraphs in the train group that don't have the bind, and one with the words' frequency in that group.
- c) It extracts the 100 most common words in training paragraphs not associated to the bind and the 30 most common words in training paragraphs associated to a bind that are not in the common non-bind words, which will be the 'bind words' used in the next steps.

2. TESTING

- a) For each testing paragraph with bind, creates a new list called *average_words* with the number of bind words found, divided by the total words.
 - b) For each testing paragraph without bind, creates a new list called *average_words* with the number of bind words found, divided by the total words.
 - c) Creates a list of all the average number of bind words for all paragraphs and calculates the average frequency to be used as a model.
- Universal Sentence Encoder (QA): The second model used is a greater-than-word length text encoder for question answer retrieval¹⁵. For the testing phase, two variants have been implemented: one that uses the rank of the distance between the embeddings (USE-RANK) and another that uses the Euclidean distance (USE-ED). The USE-RANK model uses the standardized distance, so that the nearest embedding has a standardized distance of 0.99 and farthest has a standardized distance of 0. The USE-ED calculates the inverse of the distance, so that the nearest embedding also has the highest value
 - Divide in train and test (CV leave one out): This part of the notebook creates a 10-fold Cross Validation whereby the data is split in 10 training and 10 testing datasets. For each fold, the frequency model is trained on the training set and both the Universal Sentence Encoder and the Frequency model are tested on the testing set. Note that each model is applied on single binds and language combinations iteratively. After all the folds are calculated, the testing folds are put together in a single dataframe, which is then saved in Google Drive. From the obtained dataframe, optimal thresholds (i.e. minimum difference between sensitivity and specificity) are calculated and stored on Google Drive for each model, bind and language.

¹⁵ For more information, see this reference: <https://tfhub.dev/google/universal-sentence-encoder-qa/3>

- Data analysis: The resulting dataframe is presented visually. More about this will be explained in the next section *2.1.3 Achieved results*.

2.1.3 Achieved results

Before the SSHOC project, the collective agreements in the system counted 1086, 52 countries were covered and 24 languages, now the CBA Database contains 1668 CBAs in 27 different languages, from 61 countries. The first task of the project was to increase the dataset, covering more languages and especially adding more agreements for some European languages for which there were only a few. This was necessary to make any language-based work on the data possible. Table 1 below summarises the work done on CBAs collection and annotation.

Language	SUM of TOTAL NUMBER OF CBAs in the system (14/10/2019)	SUM of TOTAL NUMBER OF CBAs in the system (19/11/2021)
EN	409	444
ES	203	268
BA	176	244
FR	121	146
IT	67	114
NL	28	102
PT	11	94
TR	8	55
DE	8	29
BN	8	27
RO	7	23
SV	6	15
DA	6	15
EL	5	13
SK	4	10
PL	4	10
HU	3	10
CZ	3	10
SL	3	8
HR	2	7
KM	1	6
VN	1	5
MT	1	4
ET	1	4
FI	0	3
LT	0	1
BG	0	1
	1086	1668

Table 1. Total number of annotate agreements per language before and after SSHOC.

Regarding task 2, see Chapter 2.1.1, the guided notebook applies and compares different models and - for each language and each question - finds which model works better in spotting the right piece of text. In the section *Data Analysis* of the notebook, the results of the testing phase are presented visually. In particular, they are shown in a scatter plot graph with area under the curve (AUC) for each bind and model (Figure 8). The higher the AUC (y-axis), the better the model performance, the higher the number of paragraphs (x-axis), the more robust the result is.

Figure 8. Scatter plot graph showing the AUC for each bind and model.

Figure 9 is a boxplot showing the area under the curve by language and model:

Figure 9. Boxplot showing the AUC for each language and model.

The plots on Figures 8-9 show that the rank-based Universal Sentence Encoder is the best performing model, although it doesn't work for all languages.

The result of this exercise is then used in the interactive tool¹⁶, where users can upload new collective agreements. The tool provides the paragraphs of the uploaded text where the answer to each question can be found. These are the steps taken by the tool:

- Load necessary libraries
- Loads the data saved from the models' notebook, namely the file with binds and labels (questions), the models and the AUC, which is used to determine which model works better for each bind in each language (i.e. has an AUC that is more than 0.8) and which is the optimal threshold. Figure 10 shows an example of this for a few binds:

bind	language	model	auc	number_of_pars	number_of_annotated_pars	optimal_threshold
wageincreasetype2	PT	use_qa_rank	0.818805	32215	3	0.902871
covercountry	DE	use_qa_rank	0.948957	5419	2	0.921757
contracttrialtxt	DE	use_qa_rank	0.961425	5419	1	0.961432
	IT	use_qa	0.947798	103982	1	0.001331
		use_qa_rank	0.827026	103982	1	0.827028
longtermillness	PT	use_qa_rank	0.970009	32215	5	0.890827
	TR	use_qa_rank	0.987029	5630	2	0.985968
lowwageamount	ES	use_qa_rank	0.969031	77702	7	0.880093
	NL	use_qa	0.938729	146775	1	0.005045
ADMINISTRATIVE_trigger	DE	use_qa_rank	0.938065	5419	2	0.879498

Figure 10. Example of AUC and optimal thresholds per language for some binds

- Loads the models
- Interactive file import and processing: section where the user can upload a new collective agreement in html, txt or docx, and select the language (Figure 11)

4. Interactive file import and processing

Figure 11. Screenshot of the section of the interactive notebook where the users can upload new documents.

¹⁶ Tool is located here:

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1R6c_vUqvkjSm9Xrnj9-1MEb_PRERd97P#scrollTo=tfU-1jWIEhle

- Process input: applies the predetermined model to identify the portion of text where the answer to the bind can be found and returns the list of binds, questions and relevant paragraphs. Figure 12 shows an example:

```

=====
How many weeks for paid annual leave are agreed for a worker with one year of service? (1 - 20) (bind: holidaysweeks)
3.El periodo de vacaciones anuales retribuidas será de treinta días
naturales o veintidós días laborales para todas las personas trabajadoras,
salvo para quienes no hubiesen completado un año de servicio en la empresa,
los cuales disfrutarán del número proporcional de días al tiempo
trabajado. (score: 1.0, model: rank)
=====

```

Figure 12. Example of a portion of the interactive notebook's output, showing the question, the bind, and the portion of text found in the uploaded document, the score and the model used.

In May 2021, this use case was applied in the Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon¹⁷, where the participants, led by Daniela Ceccon and Stefano Ceccon, were asked to work on the same datasets from the WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database. One of the most interesting ideas they developed was the calculation of the 'worker friendliness' of the text by measuring its text accessibility, which is based on two different measures, namely readability and lexical diversity. These two measures are used to observe how easy it is for the workers to understand collective agreements. Readability measures the years of education one would need to be able to understand a piece of text. This is usually evaluated through the amount of long words and long sentences. Lexical diversity looks at language from a semantic perspective and is a measure of the number of different words that are used. The hypothesis is that for a text to be considered readable, it should require fewer years of education and should have low lexical diversity. Readability and lexical diversity indices are given in a scale from 1 to 5 and are calculated on the basis of other collective agreements in the same language.

In the section *Calculate Worker Friendliness Indices*, the tool first loads the scoring functions and the dataset with the full texts of all collective agreements uploaded in the WageIndicator CBA Database. After preparing the data and setting the variables, the tool then processes the indices for the existing CBAs and calculates them for the latest uploaded agreement (e.g. Figure 13), showing also a plot of the result (Figure 14).

Readability: 3.25
Lexical Diversity: 3.0
Accessibility: 3.12

Figure 13. Example of readability, lexical diversity and accessibility indices of one uploaded text

¹⁷ Helsinki DH Hackathon:
<https://www2.helsinki.fi/en/helsinki-centre-for-digital-humanities/dhh-hackathon/helsinki-digital-humanities-hackathon-2021-dhh21>

Figure 14. Plot of the readability, lexical diversity and accessibility indices of one uploaded text.

The interactive tool has not been integrated in the WageIndicator CBA coding infrastructure, yet. The reason for this is purely technical: the coding system was built in-house by the WageIndicator IT team, so work is required on their side to integrate the tool. The idea is that, when the annotator opens the annotation page, the paragraphs are already highlighted in the text, but the annotator still has the option to change the selection, or add a different one. Also, some questions (the 'yes/no' questions) could already have 'yes' as an answer when the tool has found a clause related to that bind. There are plans to integrate the tool during the year 2022.

2.2 Integration of linguistic analysis for information extraction into SSH tasks. Use case: verbal aggression in the context of social media

2.2.1 Definition of the task

Background

Verbal Aggression (VA) involves using messages to attack other people or those aspects of their lives that are extensions of their identity (Hamilton and Hample, 2011). While VA predated the Internet, the extent and the nature of online communication tools amplifies incidents of aggression affecting billions of people; VA can manifold in a multitude of ways in different contexts with somewhat different intentions and various effects on individuals, communities, and social cohesion. Hence, the detection and the analysis of such content can help to examine individual negative and antisocial online verbal

behaviours as well as complex social phenomena (e.g., xenophobia, racism, sexism etc.). Literature review findings suggest that the detection of online aggressive content is not a trivial task; verbal attacks are shaped differently depending on individuals' intentions and strategic choices in language use, ranging from expressions of negative emotions, name calling, swearing, threatening, and insulting to the use of humor, sarcasm and irony or even paralanguage (e.g., capitalization, punctuation, emoticons) (Tereszkiewicz 2012).

Work on online aggressive language has spread across several overlapping fields causing some confusion as different works may tackle specific aspects of aggressive language, define the term differently (e.g., flaming, cyberbullying, hate speech), or apply it to specific online domains only (Nobata et al. 2016). Some studies adopt a binary classification schema aiming to distinguish hateful from non-hateful content (Köffer et al. 2018), while other studies attempt to differentiate hate speech and offensive language (Nobata et al. 2016; Davidson et al. 2017). Another line of research focuses on specific categories of hate speech, e.g., offensive tweets in terms of racist and sexist slurs based in critical race theory (Waseem and Hovy 2016). Identifying hate speech consistently is difficult and often yields the paradox that each person seems to have an intuition for what hate speech is, but rarely two people's understandings are the same (Saleem et al. 2017). For example, Waseem et al. (2017) observe that some messages considered as hate speech by Waseem and Hovy (2016) are only considered derogatory and offensive by Nobata et al. (2016) and Davidson et al. (2017). The data source also matters when examining aggression, since different online contexts (e.g., social media, hate-promoting websites) do differ in the level of aggression (Laineste 2012). Furthermore, detecting and classifying an aggressive message is not enough, since the target of the attack as well as the attacker constitute crucial elements; an effect of hate speech depends on the originator, the content and the targeted one (Chetty and Alathur, 2018). However, only a few studies incorporate these elements in their research. For example, Silva et al. (2016) provide an analysis of the main hate target groups on Twitter and Whisper, concluding that in both platforms people are mostly bullied for their ethnicity, behavior, physical characteristics, sexual orientation, and class or gender, Sanguinetti et al. (2018) deal with the creation of an Italian Twitter corpus annotated for hate speech against immigrants, while Pontiki, Papanikolaou, and Papageorgiou (2018) examine different types of verbal attacks against specific target groups of foreigners as an indicator of xenophobic attitudes in Greek Twitter during the economic crisis in Greece providing a quantitative analysis of the main targets and types of verbal attacks over time and a qualitative analysis of the main stereotypes and prejudices about these target groups.

In the context of SSHOC, ATHENA builds upon an existing VA analysis framework (Pontiki, Papanikolaou, and Papageorgiou 2018; Pontiki 2019) that was originally designed in collaboration with political scientists in the context of the XENO@GR (Examining Xenophobia in Greece, 2016). The framework consists of a linguistically inspired taxonomy of verbal attacks and a respective pipeline that applies the taxonomy at a large scale in the Greek language. As illustrated in Fig.1, the VA taxonomy considers two main types of verbally aggressive messages (VAMs) based on specific linguistic criteria: a) their focus (i.e., distinguishing between VA utterances focusing on the *target of the attack* (VAM1) and VA utterances focusing on the *attacker* (VAM2)), b) the type of linguistic weapon used for the attack (e.g. formal evaluations, obscene/dirty language, humor), structured as subtypes of VAM1 and c) the content of the attack (e.g. threats/calls for physical violence or for deportation), structured as subtypes of VAM2.

Figure 15. Typology of VAMs

In the context of T3.3. work within SSHOC, this framework is extended to new domains and topics for Greek and is also transferred in English, through specific SSH case studies in collaboration with political scientists following a standardised methodology and aiming to address specific research questions.

Research Questions

The research goal of the VA analysis framework (and the respective pipelines) is, given a collection of tweets, to address the following research questions (RQs) focusing on the targets, the type, and the content of the verbal attacks, respectively:

- **RQ1: Who are the main targets of verbal attacks?**

The VA analysis framework relies on specific predefined target entities and groups of interest depending on the case study. In its initial version within the XENO@GR project it examined the following ten predefined target groups of interest based on specific criteria (e.g., population of the specific ethnic groups in Greece, dominant prejudices in Greece about the specific groups): Pakistani, Albanians, Romanians, Syrians, Muslims/Islam, Jews, Germans, Roma, Immigrants, Refugees. In the context of SSHOC, the framework is extended to new target entities and groups (i.e., more ethnic groups and countries, political entities and groups, world leaders, media, etc.) enabling the examination of Twitter VA as an indicator of public sentiment and behaviours regarding more topics and domains. Details about the targets are provided in section 3.2.

- **RQ2: Which are the main types of verbal attacks?**

The second RQ focuses on specific types of VAMs according to the taxonomy presented above in Fig.1. Depending on the SSH case study and the targets of interest some of the VAM2 types a) may not apply (e.g., calls for aggressive assimilation (VAM2C)), or b) may have a broader use (e.g., calls/intentions for ouster/deportation (VAM2A) such as “Trump should resign”, “oust Johnson”) or a figurative use (e.g., calls/intentions for physical violence (VAM2B) such as “kill the EU”). If there is a need for a new VAM2 category (i.e., call/intention for a specific action that is important to be detected as a separate category and not as VAM2D), it can be added.

- **RQ3: What type of insights can be derived by the qualitative analysis of the verbal attacks (e.g., stereotypes, prejudices)?**

The linguistic evidence of the aggressive messages is visualized using various tools (e.g., word clouds) that contain the unique aggressive terms found per target, based on the assumption that the unique linguistic weapons used against each target may be associated with specific types of attributes or themes discussed per target. For example, the qualitative analysis of the verbal attacks against foreigners analysed in the context of the XENO@GR project confirmed the existence of stereotypes and prejudices against specific target groups that are deeply rooted in Greek society, while the qualitative analysis of the verbal attacks against political entities in the context of SSHOC, provide interesting insights regarding the ideological (left-wing and right-wing) imprints of online aggression.

Methodology

The overall workflow for applying the VA analysis framework in the context of a SSH case study involves the following steps (in iterative cycles):

1. **Case study definition.** Definition of a) the target groups or entities of interest (and the related keywords for data collection) in the context of a case study (e.g., COVID-19 and Trump, i.e. COVID-19 related tweets that mention Trump), and b) of the RQs that need to be addressed using the VA analysis output. [ATHENA, SSH scientists, i.e. University/Research centre staff]
2. **Data Collection (phase 1).** For each TG of interest relevant tweets are retrieved using the predefined queries/keywords. [ATHENA]
3. **Explorative Analysis (phase 1).** Samples of the collected raw data are explored focusing on a) the different linguistic instantiations of the targets of interest (e.g., Donald Trump, DumpTrump, etc.) as well as on other related targets within the specific case study (e.g., China), and b) the verbal attacks against these targets as well as on the types of linguistic weapons used for the attacks (i.e., linguistic instantiations of VAMs). [ATHENA, SSH scientists]
4. **Data Collection (phase 2).** Second round of data collection using also new keywords identified during phase 1 of Explorative analysis. [ATHENA]
5. **System Upgrade (phase 1).** The VA pipeline is upgraded with new resources (lexical entries and grammar modules) for target and VA detection based on the explorative analysis findings.
6. **Data Processing** using the VA pipeline. [ATHENA]

7. **Explorative Analysis (phase 2).** Samples of the output (processed data) are explored/evaluated focusing on a) the precision of the analyser (i.e., false annotations), b) the recall of the analyser (i.e., missed verbal attacks). [ATHENA, SSH scientists]
8. **System Upgrade (phase 2).** Upgrade of the system based on the explorative/error analysis findings. [ATHENA]
9. **Data Processing.** Second round of data processing, using the upgraded version of the VA pipeline. [ATHENA]
10. **Output visualization.** The VA analysis results, having been revised, are visualized in different ways (e.g., word clouds, graph charts) making them explorable, comprehensible and interpretable. [ATHENA, SSH scientists]
11. **Interpretation of the VA analysis results** with regard to the RQs. [SSH scientists, ATHENA]
12. **System Performance Evaluation** using benchmark datasets. [SSH scientists, ATHENA]

2.2.2 SSH Case Studies and Datasets

The following three case studies were implemented within SSHOC:

- **Greek case study 1: VA as an indicator of xenophobic attitudes in Greek Twitter after the financial crisis**

The first case study was a replication of the existing VA analysis framework in the post crisis era in Greece. The research goal was to re-examine VA as an indicator of xenophobic attitudes in Greek Twitter three years later, in order to trace possible changes regarding the main targets, the types and the content of the verbal attacks against the same targets after the financial crisis, given also the ongoing refugee crisis and the political landscape in Greece as it was shaped after the elections in 2019. Following the same methodology as for the period 2013-2016 (Pontiki, Papanikolaou, and Papageorgiou 2018), relevant tweets were retrieved for each target group using the same keywords. The data source for the focused Twitter collections was our in-house ATHENA/ILSP Twitter Database that we have compiled by consuming the Twitter timeline API for millions of users and gathering their full timeline which in most cases goes back to 2011. By this approach, we have constructed a database with millions of domain agnostic tweets over the years. The keyword search resulted in ten collections (one per target group), which contain a total of 1.672.783 tweets and cover the period from 1/01/2019 until 31/12/2019. The tweets were processed using the same VA pipeline (Greek_VA_analyser_v1.0) and the results were further analysed and interpreted in collaboration with Social Scientists from Panteion University with regard to the three RQs described above. The VA analysis results indicate an interesting rearrangement of the main targets of the verbal attacks, while the content and the types of the attacks provide valuable insights about the way these targets are being framed as compared to the respective dominant perceptions and stereotypes about them during the period 2013-2016. For example, Jews -the most attacked target group during 2013-2016- are shifted to the 5th place in 2019. The subsidence of the verbal attacks against Jews seems to be in accordance with the remission of the financial crisis as well as with the switchover of the political landscape in Greece in 2019; verbal attacks against them are fewer and do not convey blaming for the crisis as in the period 2013-2016. Furthermore, anti-semitic discourse in Greece has lost its main representative, the Golden Dawn party -a neo-Nazi party that evolved from a marginal group into Greece's third-largest party during the financial crisis- that was

knocked out of the Parliament, as a result of the 2019 elections. However, the types and the content of the attacks once again indicate anti-semitism as a core component of the Greek xenophobia confirming the existence of dominant perceptions that are deeply rooted in the Greek society and keep being reproduced after the financial crisis. In general, the VA analysis finding during the financial crisis in Greece provided indications the xenophobia is a deeply-rooted phenomenon in Greek society and not crisis driven, but it can escalate under circumstances of severe economic crisis (e.g. blame attribution patterns against targets related to the crisis e.g. Jews). This use case has been published in the Proceedings of the Workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud at LREC'2020 (Pontiki et al., 2020).

- **Greek case study 2: Twitter VA in the context of political violence in Greece**

The research goal of this case study was to examine verbal attacks expressed against specific political entities and groups as an aspect of political violence in Greek Twitter during 2019 and 2020 focusing on four protagonist political actors in the Greek scene as targets of VA: a) New Democracy (the conservative party that won the 2019 election and now leads the country's government), (b) Kyriakos Mitsotakis (the current Greek Prime Minister and leader of New Democracy), (c) Syriza (the Coalition of Radical Left party that was ousted from government in 2019), and (d) Alexis Tsipras (Greece's former Prime Minister and leader of Syriza and of the current Official Opposition). To this end, focused Twitter data collections have been created containing a total of 3,675,107 tweets and covering the period from 01/01/2019 to 31/08/2020. This twenty-month period was selected due to the transition of power after the Greek general elections of 2019, and the following first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak in 2020. The data collection was based on 418 keywords-possible lexicalizations of the four targets of interest and the data source was again the ATHENA/ILSP Twitter Database. The collected tweets were processed using the new version of the Greek VA pipeline (2.0) that has been upgraded with the respective resources and modules for the politics domain in the context of SSHOC (see below section 2.2.3). The VA analysis findings -that were further analysed and interpreted with regard to the three basic RQs in collaboration with political scientists from Panteion University- provided interesting insights regarding the levels, the main frames and the ideological (left-wing and right-wing) imprints of online aggression, while their contextualization within the broader political environment in which they took place makes apparent the most underlying and invisible aspect of political violence, the symbolic violence. For example, the VA findings within the transition of power permit us to follow the politics of blame by exploring if a governmental swift changes the main targets of online verbal attacks, while the pandemic outbreak and its subsequent confinement gives us the chance to observe to what extent online VA has been influenced by these unprecedented experiences. This use case will be published in the Journal of Modern Greek Studies [Special Section on Political Violence in Greece], Johns Hopkins University Press (Pontiki et al., 2022).

- **English case study: Donald Trump as a target and an originator of VA in the context of COVID-19 pandemic (English)**

This case study aims to examine the impact of Trump's aggressive rhetoric as regards the pandemic (if any). In this sense, the data collected included tweets featuring both Trump and COVID-19. In collaboration with political scientists from SciencesPo, we analysed and classified tweets into three categories (covering the period January 2020- August 2020) where VA, COVID-19 and Trump are included:

- Category 1= tweets by Trump (tweets where @realDonaldTrump is the user that sent the tweet);
- Category 2 = tweets by opponents/critics (where the target of VA is Trump);
- Category 3 = tweets by others, supporters and neutral (where target is not equal to Trump AND user not equal @realDonaldTrump).

The datasets for the above categories were created as follows:

- Category 1: We retrieved from the publicly available COVID-19 database (<https://github.com/echen102/COVID-19-tweetIDs>) the 208 tweets originated by Trump (user account @realdonaldtrump (id 25073877), user account @POTUS (id for Trump 822215679726100480)) and also from <https://www.thetrumparchive.com/> the 509 covid related tweets originated by Trump the period under investigation (January 2020-August 2020). Duplicate tweets have been removed, ending up to a collection of 636 COVID-related, Trump-originated tweets, based on the above two data sources.
- Categories 2 and 3: We retrieved from the publicly available COVID-19 database (<https://github.com/echen102/COVID-19-tweetIDs>) 311,219,718 tweets covering the time period from 21/01/2020 to 31/08/2020. Subsequently, we created a focused collection of 32,261,669 COVID-19 related tweets that mention Donald Trump using a set of 398 keywords - possible lexicalizations of Trump e.g., Trump, #DonaldTrump, #trump, Trumplings, #ResignTrump.

The datasets were processed using the English VA analysis pipeline that was designed and implemented in the context of SSHOC (see below section 2.2.3). The VA analysis findings were further analysed and interpreted in collaboration with political scientists from SciencePo with regard to specific RQs. revealing interesting insights regarding Trump both as an aggressor and as a target of verbal attacks during the pandemic.

2.2.3 VA Analysis Pipeline

For the semantic analysis of Social Media content, and in particular for detecting VA exhibited in interactions on the Twitter platform, ATHENA has devised and developed a VA analysis framework, consisting of:

- the existing linguistic analysis pipeline for Greek content (ATHENA/ILSP suite of NLP tools), undertaking the task of basic linguistic annotation in terms of sentence boundary detection and token/word delimitation, part-of speech tagging, and lemmatization (available through CLARIN:EL (www.clarin.gr) at <http://hdl.grnet.gr/11500/ATHENA-0000-0000-23E9-2>), and
- two specially developed semantic analysis pipelines for Greek and English, respectively, undertaking the task of detecting and annotating VA expressing patterns according to the typology of VAMs described in the previous section.

The approach for the detection of verbal attacks is lexicon-based and explores shallow syntactic relations between aggressive terms (i.e. words that are used to express VA) and sequences of tokens-candidate targets of the attacks, using linguistic patterns. The overall architecture of the VA analysis framework is illustrated in Fig. 2. The input for the VA analyser is raw data (Twitter collections). In the first phase the data are processed through a Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline that

performs tokenization, sentence splitting, part-of-speech tagging, and lemmatization/morphological analysis using the respective ATHENA/ILSP suite of NLP tools for Greek using the ILSP suite of NLP tools for Greek (Papageorgiou et al. 2002; Prokopidis, Georgantopoulos and Papageorgiou 2011) and the respective ANNIE tools included in GATE (General Architecture for Text Engineering, open source software toolkit for text processing, <https://gate.ac.uk/>) (Cunningham et al., 2002) for English. In the next phase, the pre-processing output is fed as input to the Semantic Analysis Unit, which performs VA analysis based on a variety of lexical resources and grammars (sets of linguistic patterns). The general architecture is the same for the Greek and the English VA Analysers. The lexical resources and the linguistic patterns as well as the linguistic processing pipelines are language specific.

Figure 16. Architecture for VA analysis

The VA analyser is a Finite State Transducers (FST) cascade implemented as a JAPE grammar (Cunningham, Maynard and Tablan 2000) in the GATE framework (Cunningham et al. 2002). These FSTs process annotation streams with regular expressions to create generalized rules. Moreover, they are ordered in a cascade, so that the output of an FST is given as input to the next transducer. In the first phase, the analyser detects candidate VAMs and candidate targets based on the respective lexical resources; if a token is recognized as a lexicon entry, then it is annotated with the respective metadata (lexicon labels). In the subsequent step, the grammars determine which spotted candidate VAMs and targets are correct (since the co-occurrence of an aggressive term and a candidate target in a tweet does not necessarily entail a verbal attack against the particular target). For each identified VAM, the method returns the type and the linguistic evidence of the attack as well as the id and the linguistic evidence of the target of the attack (TG). For example, for the tweet: “Yes, Trump is a psychopath. #TrumpResignNow”, the analyser returns the following 2 tuples:

```
<TG_id: "TG11", TG_evidence: "Trump", VAM_type: "VAM1A", VA_evidence: "psychopath">.
<TG_id: "TG11", TG_evidence: "#TrumpResignNow", VAM_type: "VAM2A", VA_evidence:
"#TrumpResignNow">.
```

The method is precision-oriented and focuses on explicitly stated VA; it relies on a set of lexical resources that are built to capture possible linguistic instantiations of VA towards the targets of interest. VAMs that are instantiated through complex linguistic structures and devices (i.e., humor, irony, implicit calls for action), and cannot be captured at the lexical level are not addressed currently by the VA analysers.

2.2.3.1 Greek VA Analyser

As already described in previous sections, the first version of the Greek VA Analyser (v1.0) was designed and implemented in the context of the XENO@GR project to examine the following ten predefined target groups of interest based on specific criteria (i.e., Pakistani, Albanians, Romanians, Syrians, Muslims/Islam, Jews, Germans, Roma, Immigrants, Refugees). In the context of SSHOC, an upgraded version of the Greek VA Analyser (v2.0) was designed and implemented extending the VA analysis framework to new target entities and groups which were prominent in the public scene during the current period, focusing mainly on the politics domain as follows:

- Political parties in Greece and politicians of these parties: New Democracy (ND), Syriza etc.
- Political Leaders: Kyriakos Mitsotakis, Alexis Tsipras, etc.
- The current President of Democracy in Greece
- Media and Journalists
- Police
- The head of the COVID-19 management committee in Greece (an infectologist).

This extension enables the examination of Twitter VA also as an indicator of other than xenophobic stances and behaviours. Through the case study implemented in SSHOC, the upgraded version of the Greek VA pipeline was used to examine VA as an aspect of political violence in Greek Twitter focusing on protagonist political actors in the Greek scene and on the following types of verbal attacks according to the VA taxonomy:

- **VAM1A.** Verbal attacks expressing criticism through negative evaluations of specific attributes of the target(s) of the attacks, such as the adjectival modifiers Ανίδεοι (ignorant) and εθνικά επικίνδυνοι (dangerous for the nation) in (1), the nouns ψεύτη (liar) and προδότη (traitor) in (2), and the hashtag #κυβέρνηση_τίρκο (circus government) in (3).

(1) Ανίδεοι και εθνικά επικίνδυνοι ο κ. Μητσοτάκης και η ΝΔ. (Mr Mitsotakis and ND are ignorant and dangerous for the nation).

- **VAM1B.** Taboo or dirty language (e.g., swearing, slang, etc.) like Άντε γαμήσου (Fuck off) and λέρα (filth, grime) in (2), χαλβά (halvah, meaning feeble person) in (4), and κωλόπαιδο (asshole) in (5).

(2) @atsipras Άντε γαμήσου ρε λέρα ψεύτη προδότη. (@atsipras Fuck off you filthy liar traitor).

- **VAM1C.** Attacks lexicalized through complex linguistic devices and structures (e.g., humor and irony) like the ironic use of the word διάνοια (genius), the hashtag #le_petit_koulis (Koulis is a rather derogatory nickname for Kyriakos Mitsotakis) and the whole ironic or somewhat humorous tint in (3).

(3) Όλες οι εξουσίες στη διάνοια #le_petit_koulis. Σαν να βλέπεις θρίλερ, κωμωδία κι επιστημονική φαντασία μαζί. #κυβέρνηση_Μητσοτάκη #κυβέρνηση_τσίρκο (All the power to the genius #le_petit_koulis. It is like watching a thriller, a comedy and science fiction at the same time #government_Mitsotakis #government_circus).

- **VAM2A.** Verbal attacks expressing intentions or calls for ouster like the directive speech act Παρατήσου (resign) in (4).

(4) @kmitsotakis Παρατήσου επιτέλους ρε χαλβά!!! (@kmitsotakis finally resign you halvah!!!).

- **VAM2B.** Verbal attacks expressing intentions or calls for physical violence/harm or physical extinction like ψόφα (die) in (5).

(5) @atsipras Αι ψόφα ρε κωλόπαιδο να γλιτώσει ο τόπος. (@atsipras Die you asshole for the country's sake.)

As indicated by the above examples, a tweet may contain more than one verbal attack against the same target or against more than one target. Each verbal attack is considered a unique VAM and is classified according to the above taxonomy based on a set of lexical resources and linguistic grammars as described below.

Greek VA Pipeline Resources

The Greek VA analysis system relies on the following manually created lexical resources:

- VA1 Lexicon. A customized version of the Greek version of EvalLex (Pontiki, Angelou, and Papageorgiou, 2013) an Appraisal Theory (Martin and White, 2005) grounded Lexicon for Evaluative Language that was manually compiled for the Greek and the English languages. In particular, the evaluative terms with negative orientation were further grouped in two semantic categories: VAM1A for formal evaluations (e.g., επικίνδυνος (dangerous)), VAM1B for obscene vocabulary (e.g., κάθαρμα (bastard)) and VAM1C for ironic language. The lexicon was further enriched with new entries based on data exploration findings.
- VAM2 Lexicon. Terms used to express attacks focusing on the aggressor's intentions (VAM2) e.g., παραιτούμαι (resign), διώχνω (oust, kick out), σκοτώνω (murder). Each term is assigned a label according to its category (e.g., noun or verb) and the aggression type it indicates (i.e., VAM2A, VAM2B). Verbs are further classified into specific types based on their syntactic

behavior: VB1 for intransitive verbs and expressions (e.g., αποχωρώ (resign, depart)), and VB2 for transitive verbs and expressions (e.g., διώχνω (kick out)).

- TG (target) Lexicon. Possible lexicalizations of target entities and groups e.g., μουσουλμάνος (muslim), αλβανικός (Albanian), Νέα Δημοκρατία (New Democracy), Κυριάκος Μητσοτάκης (Kyriakos Mitsotakis).
- TGVA Lexicon. Possible lexicalizations of the TGs that express at the same time VA towards them such as racial and ethnic slurs (e.g., αλβαναριό for Albanians, cf. Wogs, the English racial name for Mediterranean/Greek people) or compound words and derogatory morphological variations of names (e.g., petit koulis for Kyriakos Mitsotakis).
- Modifiers Lexicon. A typical sentiment analysis resource that contains intensifiers (e.g., εντελώς (totally)), downtoners (e.g., κάπως (somewhat)), and negators (e.g., καθόλου (not at all)).

In the first version of the system the lexical resources contained 2596 entries in total. In the upgraded version of the system (Gr_VA_Analyzer_v2.0) implemented through SSHOC the lexical resources have been enriched with new vocabulary both for VA and new targets reaching a total of 6376 entries.

As it has been described above, the lexical resources are used to detect candidate verbal attacks and targets. In a subsequent step, linguistic grammars impose restrictions in the context around the spotted candidate verbal attacks and targets and determine which of them are true, since the appearance of an aggressive term and a linguistic instantiation of a given target in a text does not necessarily entail a verbal attack against it in all contexts. The grammars are the implementation of multi-phase algorithms where the output of each phase is the input for the next one. Each phase comprises several modules that contain a variety of contextual lexico-syntactic patterns. The patterns are templates that generate rules in the context around candidate verbal attacks and targets using shallow syntactic relations. In particular, the analyser comprises two grammars, one for each basic type of VA:

- VAM1 Grammar performs stepwise VA and target detection using combinations between TG and VA1 Lexicon entries.
- VAM2 Grammar performs stepwise VA and target detection using combinations between TG and VA2 Lexicon entries.

In the first version of the system, the grammars contained 94 lexico-syntactic patterns in total. In the upgraded version of the system (Gr_VA_Analyzer_v2.0) implemented through SSHOC the linguistic grammars have been enriched with new patterns that model more types of lexico-syntactic relations between aggressive terms and targets of verbal attacks reaching a total of 202 patterns.

Greek VA Analyser Evaluation

The pipeline is evaluated using a benchmark dataset built to serve as a test set in the context of the case study that examines VA in the context of political violence in Greece. The test set consists of 1,000 tweets (250 per each target of interest: Kyriakos Mitsotakis, Alexis Tsipras, New Democracy, and Syriza). The tweets were selected carefully to achieve a representative sample of the different cases that the VA analyser must deal with (i.e., tweets containing different types of verbal attacks against the targets using a variety of linguistic devices, tweets mentioning the target entities but attacking other targets, tweets mentioning the target entities but not conveying VA). The dataset was annotated by two postgraduate students, native speakers of Greek. First, the annotators were trained through lectures

and annotation exercises. Then, they were provided with detailed annotation guidelines and they annotated the test set using the INCEpTION semantic annotation platform (Klie et al., 2018) available through the CLARIN:EL infrastructure. When the annotation task was completed, two expert annotators inspected all the annotations, resolved the disagreements between the two postgraduates and decided about the final labels in borderline cases. Then, the engine annotated data was compared to the gold data (human annotated). The performance of the analyser is measured in terms of Precision (P), Recall (R) and F-Measure (F-1) defined as follows:

$$P = \frac{|S \cap G|}{|S|} \quad R = \frac{|S \cap G|}{|G|} \quad F_1 = \frac{2 \cdot P \cdot R}{P + R}$$

S is the set of the VA tuples that the system returned for all the test tweets, and G is the set of the gold (correct) VA tuples-annotations. F1 score is the harmonic mean of P and R .

	Precision	Recall	F-measure
Mitsotakis	90%	62%	74%
Tsipras	86%	58%	69%
ND	94%	72%	82%
Syriza	94%	68%	79%
Average	91%	65%	76%

Table 2: Greek VA Analyser Evaluation Results.

The experimental evaluation results confirmed the expectations favoring a precision-oriented method. As illustrated in Table 1, the system achieves an overall precision of 91%. As also expected for a rule-based method, the recall is not so high (average 65%), since the method cannot address verbal attacks that are instantiated through complex linguistic structures and devices and cannot be captured at the lexical level, since they require extralinguistic knowledge. In addition, recall is negatively affected due also to misspellings and typos that do not allow the activation of the lexical resources and due the limitations of the shallow syntactic relations modelling, since long distance dependencies cannot be captured through a window of a limited number of tokens. In some cases, the recall drops because of multiple mentions of the targets (e.g., both @atsipras and Alexis in a tweet); the system correctly detects verbal attacks but assigns them to a different mention of the target than the human annotators did. Overall, the evaluation results and the error analysis findings suggest that the method sufficiently addresses explicitly stated VA. An interesting finding is that the system performs better when detecting verbal attacks in the focused collections about ND and Syriza as compared to the ones for Mitsotakis and Tsipras. This might indicate that VA against political leaders is expressed through a greater lexical variety and more complex linguistic structures as compared to the verbal attacks against political parties.

2.2.3.2 English VA Analyzer

The English VA analysis pipeline is built from scratch in the context of T3.3. work within SSHOC. In its first version (En_VA_Analyzerv1.0), the system is designed to address the following types of verbal attacks according to the VA taxonomy:

- **VAM1A:** Verbal attacks expressing criticism through negative evaluations of specific attributes of the target(s) of the attacks such as Hypocrisy about Democrats in *“Democrats’ Hypocrisy on Riots Reveals Political Nature of Coronavirus Lockdowns”*.
- **VAM1B** (merged with VAM1C): Taboo, dirty, insulting, or ironic language like Chinese Virus in *“The United States will be powerfully supporting those industries, like Airlines and others, that are particularly affected by the Chinese Virus”*.
- **VAM2A:** Verbal attacks expressing intentions or calls for ouster e.g., RESIGN and TrumpResignNow in *“RT @juliabhaber: TRUMP MUST RESIGN!!!!!!!!!!!!!! #TrumpResignNow”*
- **VAM2B:** Verbal attacks expressing intentions or calls for physical violence/harm or physical extinction e.g., wipe out in *“Man we could wipe out Trump supporters in one shot? HmMMMM”*

For the development of the analyser Brexit and COVID-19 related data were used. Based on explorative analysis findings, the case study under examination, and feedback provided by SciencesPo this first version of the system is designed to address verbal attacks against the following targets (ethnic groups, political entities, geopolitical entities, organisations, etc.) of interest:

- Muslims/Islam
- Jews
- Immigrants
- Refugees
- Organizations: World Health Organization (W.H.O.), European Union (EU), International Monetary Fund (IMF), United Nations (UN)
- Geopolitical entities: United States of America (USA), China, United Kingdom (UK)
- Political entities: Donald Trump, Boris Johnson, Joe Biden, Barack Obama, Nancy Pelosi, Mitch McConnell, Mike Pence, Chuck Schumer, Andrew Cuomo
- Anthony Fauci (the Director of the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases who served as one of the lead members of the White House Coronavirus Task Force during the COVID-19 pandemic).
- Democrats
- Republicans
- Media
- Brexit

English VA Pipeline Resources

The English VA pipeline follows the architecture of the Greek pipeline; for the transition of the Greek pipeline in English the respective lexical resources and grammars have been implemented. In particular, the VA analyser relies on the following manually created lexical resources:

- VA1 Lexicon. A customized version of the English version of EvalLex (Pontiki, Angelou, and Papageorgiou, 2013) used for the detection of VAMs that focus on the attributes of the target of the verbal attack. In particular, the evaluative terms with negative orientation were further grouped in two semantic categories: VAM1A for formal evaluations (e.g., arrogant) and VAM1B for obscene/ironic language (e.g., moron). The lexicon was further enriched with new entries based on data exploration findings.
- VA2 Lexicon. Terms (translated from the respective Greek VA2 Lexicon) used to express verbal aggression focusing on the aggressor's intentions (VAM2) e.g., *oust, murder, get out of here, execution*. Each term is assigned a label according to its part-of-speech category (e.g., noun or verb) and the aggression type it indicates (i.e., VAM2A, VAM2B). Verbs are further classified into specific types based on their syntactic behavior: VB1/VB1p (Phrasal verbs) for transitive verbs and expressions (e.g., deport, get rid of, chase away), VB2 for intransitive verbs and expressions (e.g., leave, go away), and VB3 for interjections (e.g., bugger off, avaunt).
- TG Lexicon. Possible lexicalizations of target entities and groups so far e.g., *muslim, islamic, Boris Johnson, China, Donald Trump*.
- TGVA Lexicon. Possible lexicalizations of the TGs that express at the same time VA towards them such as racial and ethnic slurs (e.g., mockey, towelhead) or compound words e.g., dumptrump.
- Modifiers Lexicon. A typical sentiment analysis resource that contains intensifiers (e.g., totally), downtoners (e.g., somewhat), and negators (e.g., not at all).

The lexical resources contain 3562 entries so far and are implemented as jape modules through GATE.

The grammars are also based on the Greek grammars but taking into account the individualities of the English grammar and syntax:

- VAM1 Grammar for VA and target detection using combinations between TG and VA1 Lexicon entries.
- VAM2 Grammar for VA and target detection using combinations between TG and VA2 Lexicon entries.

In the current version implemented through SSHOC (En_VA_Analyzer_v1.0) the two grammars contain a total of 98 lexico-syntactic patterns that generate rules in the context around candidate verbal attacks and targets.

English VA Analyser Evaluation

The pipeline is evaluated using a benchmark dataset built to serve as a test set. In collaboration with SciencesPo, a random set of 605 tweets (unique tweet ids) attacking Trump was selected and annotated by two native English speakers following specific instructions. 133 of these tweets were retweets reproducing the exact tweet text (i.e., 472 unique tweets). These retweets were not removed from the annotation set in order to check the consistency of the annotators when coding tweets with the exact tweet text. The annotators used the Label Studio open-source data labelling tool that was configured appropriately for the specific annotation task to include the following labels:

- TG_evidence: the mention of the target of the attack (i.e., Donald Trump)

- VA_evidence: the linguistic expression of the verbal attack (based on a taxonomy of specific types of verbal attacks)

To measure the reliability of our study, we report two inter-annotator agreement measures i) Krippendorff's unitizing α and ii) gamma (Mathet, 2015). For the Krippendorff's unitizing α coefficient we present the most recent proposed version (Krippendorff et al., 2016) with the $_{u}\alpha$ -family of agreement coefficients. In detail the reliability coefficient $_{u}\alpha$ which measures the reliability of a study regarding the positioning of the annotations and the measure $_{cu}\alpha$ which shows the reliability of a study regarding the two categories (VA, TG) of the intersected identified units.

	605 (tweets and retweets)	472 (unique tweets)
$_{u}\alpha$	0.567	0.58
$_{cu}\alpha$	0.972	0.966
γ (Gamma)	0.62	0.63

Table 3. IAA scores

The $_{cu}\alpha=0.972$ indicates that the agreement on the categorization level (identifying verbal attacks against a target) is high and points out that the categorization of the identified units could be considered reliable. The Gamma measure takes both unitizing and categorization under consideration and reports an agreement of 0.63. The $_{u}\alpha = 0.58$ indicates that the agreement on unitizing level is not so good. The qualitative analysis of the annotators' disagreements on the unitizing level revealed 601 cases of disagreements of one or two characters in the offsets of the annotations e.g., annotator 1 systematically included the space character after the last character of the annotated text e.g., "Trump" instead of "Trump", when the mention of Trump (TG_evidence) includes an apostrophe (i.e., Trump's) annotator 1 systematically annotated the whole span (Trump's), while annotator 2 systematically annotated "Trump", when annotating hashtags (e.g., #TrumpPandemic), annotator 2 systematically included the # in the text span, while annotator 1 not. Furthermore we encountered some disagreements between lexical versus phrase level VA expressions (e.g., in "*Donald Trump's cruelty truly knows no bounds*" annotator 2 coded as VA "*cruelty truly knows no bounds*", while annotator 1 delivered two separate VA annotations "*cruelty*" and "*knows no bounds*") as well as on the VA annotations (minimum vs maximum phrase) boundaries (e.g., "*greater threat than the Coronavirus*" (annotator1) versus "*threat*" (annotator2) for "*@gtconway3d Trump is a greater threat than the Coronavirus*". Overall, the IAA analysis findings as well as the quantitative and the qualitative analysis of the annotators' own disagreements when coding duplicate tweets suggest that the two annotators delivered consistent and trustworthy annotations.

Based on the annotations delivered by the two annotators for the 472 tweets we created a benchmark dataset for the evaluation of the VA analysis tool using the GATE framework. The disagreements between the two annotators were resolved by an expert annotator. The benchmark dataset contains a total of 789 VA annotations (TG & VA evidence). To evaluate the performance of the system, the engine annotated data was compared to the gold data (human annotated). The performance of the analyser is measured in terms of Precision (P), Recall (R) and F-Measure (F-1) both at the phrase level (i.e., evaluating the performance for each verbal attack) and at the tweet level (i.e., calculating the

percentage of the tweets correctly and falsely recognised as aggressive (containing at least one verbal attack against Trump)).

	Precision	Recall	F-measure
Phrase level	88%	59%	71%
tweet level	88%	92%	90%

Table 4. English VA Analyser Evaluation Results.

The experimental evaluation results confirmed the expectations favoring a precision-oriented method. As illustrated below, the system achieves an overall precision of 88%. As also expected for a rule-based method, performance of the system is better when measured at the tweet level, since many tweets contain multiple attacks about the same target. Hence, the recall is significantly higher when the system must detect at least one verbal attack and classify a tweet as aggressive (92%) as compared to identifying all the verbal attacks in a tweet (59%). For example, in “RT @Drummer66X: @sendavidperdue @realDonaldTrump Yep, the Covid cases are already spiking out of control again...Donald ??Open It Up?? Trump is such a narcissist he truly believes he is smarter than the scientists & doctors. I cant believe this lying joker is our president...God help us. #NotMyPresident” the system correctly identifies “such a narcissist” as an attack against Trump but cannot capture the attacks “lying joker” and “#NotMyPresident” that require coreference resolution and long-distance dependencies modelling. At the tweet level evaluation this tweet is correctly classified as aggressive against Trump, while at the phrase level evaluation the recall is affected by the missing attacks. Furthermore, the recall is negatively affected in cases of complex structures, usually irony, that cannot be addressed at the lexical level and require extralinguistic knowledge. The precision is negatively affected mainly in tweets reproducing verbal attacks against Trump with the aim to support Trump and attack his attackers (e.g. RT @joe_hunglo: Trump is racist and wrong for calling #COVID19 the “Chinah Virus.” liberals Will they just once, accept that Trump is always right? @Sassiest1girl #ChinaVirus), and in cases of irony. Overall, the evaluation results and the error analysis findings suggest that the method addresses sufficiently explicitly stated VA.

2.3 TDM handling of heterogeneous data. Use case: Intertextuality phenomena in European drama history

2.3.1 Definition of the task

The initial research question and hypothesis which is born out of literary studies, is the following: in most European dramas of the 16th/17th century—English, Spanish, French (and Italian) likewise—the character of a “servant” or other representatives of lower social classes have the function to unveil the hidden order of discourse by incorporating a comical wisdom which can be solely represented by minor characters. Regardless of the major differences in European drama history during this period of

classical and baroque theatre, we assume that the characteristic voice of the “servant” can be detected across a multilingual drama corpus of English, French and Spanish texts.

As this era is also characterised as the most productive time in the history of European theatre, a large body of those texts are available for research. Although it depends on the quality and the format of the available texts, they are finally promising resources for running the very same experiments for different languages and for adding statistical evidence to hypotheses in literary studies. Therefore, an automatic identification of individual characters' speeches in a large corpus of plays provides an opportunity to better understand the role of these minor characters at large scale, and to analyse a very specific movement and intertextuality phenomena in European drama history.

In order to discover such figures and their spoken text it is indispensable to find out who is speaking and who is on stage in all these dramas. In the context of T3.3. work within SSHOC, DARIAH/UGOE and CLARIN/CUNI partners have investigated how different NLP methods and tools can be used to support this research task: (a) comparative literary analysis; and (b) an analysis of the literary language of individual dramas of the respective historical language level. For this purpose, the spoken texts of ‘servants’ and ‘jesters’ in a selected corpus of comedies from the 16th and 17th centuries are examined.

2.3.2 Dataset description

The compilation of the multilingual corpus follows a literary historical line which can be traced from Shakespeare (1590—1616) via the Spanish comedia, including texts from Lope de Vega, Calderón de la Barca, Tirso de Molina and many more, (1585—1670) to the French classical theatre with Molière et al. (1640—1695) with borrowings from the Italian Commedia dell'Arte. Side characters such as a ‘servant’ or a ‘jester’ are often hidden main characters, because they repeat the ‘heroic speech’ of main characters from a different perspective through a humorous reflection of it.

In order to answer the research question, first, texts of all dramas must be available in valid TEI format and spoken text of at least both groups of characters (servants and masters) needed to be identified inside of each text. The identification of the social role of each character in each play could not be performed automatically but needed intellectual annotation. Second, individual characters’ speeches need to be extracted and saved as plain text files. Third, content of these plain text files has to be processed with NLP software. Fourth, using respective NLP tools helps to further develop and exploit their potential for different languages and language levels, likewise.

2.3.3 Achieved results

Corpus preparation and preprocessing

Three different corpora were provided by the UGOE partner and either crawled from <https://dracor.org/> (English, Calderón (Spanish language) and French corpus in TEI-XML) or given from a private collection, as it is the case for the [Spanish corpus Calderón](#) in plain text format. All texts are freely available as public domain. All texts, data and software will be published in gitlab and a community specific repository, thus they can be used by literary scholars interested in a specific

language as well as by scholars of Comparative and Computational Literary Studies. The process of making the data available in TEI P5 format is complete for 411 dramas's texts that are ready for evaluation:

- 37 in English,
- 203 in French and
- 171 in Spanish.

All 37 English, all 203 French dramas and some 114 of 171 Spanish ones are already valid against [tei_all.rng](#) scheme whilst the rest is still in progress. In all 37 English and 44 Spanish dramas—i.e. 81 pieces in total—social status of each character has been manually encoded in `<castList>` (eg. `<castItem n="nobility">`, `<castItem n="soldier">` etc.).

Due to diversity of data given a fixed workflow converting all files to both plain text files of identical form and to valid TEI-XML for all three languages—English, French and Spanish—could not be designed. First, parts of corpora of all three languages have been from the beginning available solely in TEI-XML and others exclusively as plain text files. Second, some XML are not valid against any schema, and some plain text files were, in different ways, proprietary encoded. Therefore, different transformation- (XSLT) and Python scripts¹⁸ have been written for different parts of the corpus.

For samples of plays, [DraCor](#) is used: [Shakespeare Drama Corpus](#) for English, [CaldraCor](#) (<https://dracor.org/cal>) for Spanish, and [French Drama Corpus](#) for French. It is a corpus of TEI-XML P5 annotated dramas, containing meta-information about the speakers such as character names, their respective spoken text, stage directions etc. From these files first each character's spoken text has been extracted as single plain text file to be processed with UDPipe, afterwards, and second it has been checked if **all** characters's spoken text has been extracted via numerical comparison of the number of `<person>` in `<listPerson>` in each drama's TEI file with the number of extracted plain text files. The processing steps can be summarised as follows:

1. Collect the statistics about the dataset, e.g. number of characters (`<person>`) across the dramas
2. Extract masters' and servants' spoken text as single plain text, and structure these plain text files according to the source dramas
3. Run check of the result for consistency.

The detailed steps of this pipeline can be checked on the GitHub - [link](#). We have also created a SSH Open Marketplace Workflow describing the pipeline - [link](#).

The above described workflow was applied on all of the mentioned corpora. The results (extracted single character's speeches) and for a selection of the corpus also the annotation of the social group will be published in order to enable less technical oriented researchers in the Humanities to use them directly with low level text analysis tools like (CLARIN LRS, stylometry, voyant, CATMA, etc.). The creation of comparable corpora in different languages, already annotated and with single plain text files for each character, invites a broader community to reuse the data and provides a low-threshold access to data driven research in the Humanities.

¹⁸ All relevant Python scripts can be found at <https://github.com/ufal/SSHOC>

Other part of the corpus of Spanish dramas has been available solely as plain text files and therefore first also has to be converted into valid well-formed TEI-XML. We have semi-automated the conversion process using a script and a set of human-provided “marks”.¹⁹ The marks provided by the user serve to indicate the basic drama meta-information (e.g. name of the drama, name of the author), indicate the beginning-end of the list of characters and beginning-end of the drama itself. Additional marks are used to indicate beginning-end of individual character utterances and beginning-end of the individual parts of the drama. By providing these marks in the original plaintext, the script then inserts the necessary XML-structure following the naming convention, removing the need of inserting the XML tags manually.

Description of the research question

In order to create a blueprint of what we want to prove with the TDM and NLP method and to be able to compare the results of close and distant reading, the research question has been specified exemplarily for four plays:

1. Tirso de Molina: *El burlador de Sevilla* (c. 1630)
2. Jean Racine: *Phèdre* (1677)
3. Pedro Calderón de la Barca: *El médico de su honra* (1637)
4. Molière: *Dom Juan ou Le Festin de Pierre* (1665)

If we try to describe several functionalities of servants or other socially minor figures in the 17th century European drama, there are some which are related to linguistics and probably detectable by NLP and others which are very much more related to complex rhetorical methods and figures, expressed in humour and irony which are not likely to be detected by NLP.

We distinguish in the following four different characteristics and functionalities:

1. The servant acts as a **messenger or commentator** of actions:
In the *Burlador de Sevilla*, the famous Don Juan play which is attributed to Tirso de Molina, the unnamed servant (*criado*) serves as the voice of the Spanish ambassador. It is unusual for the messenger (e.g. in the classical Greek drama) to refer to himself like the servant does in this case (“entendí / yo mal, entiendo”).

CRIADO: *El embajador de España*
en este punto se apea
en el zaguán, y desea,
con ira y fiereza estraña,
hablarte, y si no entendí
yo mal, entiendo es prisión.
[Act I; 243-250]

Another example is the equally famous French classical tragedy *Phèdre* by Racine, in which the person who is most close to the female protagonist and plays a major role is her servant Oenone. She can be made at least partly responsible for the suicide of Phèdre and her quantity of speech in comparison to the main character Phèdre is considerable large: Oenone (1708

¹⁹ <https://github.com/ufal/SSHOC/blob/main/Task-3.3/scripts/python/txt2tei.py>

words); Phèdre (3942 words). Oenone has several functionalities inside of the drama. In her messenger role she is always rather intimate and emotional and directed to her master, Phèdre:

OENONE: *Madame, je cessais de vous presser de vivre.*

Déjà même au tombeau je songeais à vous suivre.

Pour vous en détourner je n'avais plus de voix.

Mais ce nouveau malheur vous prescrit d'autres lois.

Votre fortune change et prend une autre face.

Le roi n'est plus, Madame, il faut prendre sa place.

Sa mort vous laisse un fils à qui vous vous devez,

Esclave, s'il vous perd, et roi, si vous vivez.

[Act I; V.337-344]

In this case the false information of the presumably death of the king and husband is the key to start the whole tragedy. In both examples, the Spanish and the French play, the mixture of personal, intimate style, expressed in personal pronouns (yo, je) and the actual report of facts ("El embajador [...] se apea"; "Le roi n'est plus") can be described as distinguishable similarities in the servants speech. Digital methods using NLP like POS tagging and text comparison, vocabulary comparison or others could be tested if they are able to detect these kinds of differences and similarities on a larger scale level. In order to be able to proceed with this idea each extracted character speech needs to be manually annotated and labelled according to their social role.

2. The servant acts as the **moral advocate towards the misbehaviour of his or her master**:

Again the comedia, *El burlador de Sevilla* can be used as an example. In the first scene of seduction: Don Juan seduces two fisher women and forces his servant, Catalinon to help him. While Catalinon has to obey to his master, he still expresses in a rather hidden and philosophical way his distress and the moral falseness of the act:

CATALINON: *En desventura iguales,*

pescadora, muchos males,

y falta de muchos bienes,

Veo, por librarme a mí,

sin vida a mi señor. Mira

si es verdad,.

[Act I; 555-559]

There is a stylistic change in the very same part of Catalinon's speech: The first lines are written like a moralistic poem with a repetitive rhyme. Only the second part is the actual delivery of the given task. All the moral exposure of the master's misbehaviour needs to be secretly done by the servant even if Catalinon spells the fate of Don Juan explicitly ("lo pagaréis en la muerte" - you will pay for it in death) it is not taken seriously by the master, because he considers his servant as irrelevant and minor in social status.

CATALINON: *Los que fingís y engaáis*

*las mujeres de esa suerte,
lo pagaréis en la muerte.*
[Act I; 902-905]

- The servant acts as **a forced supporter of her or his masters** against her or his expressed will. In Molière's adaptation of the same topic *Don Juan ou Le Festin de Pierre* a variation of the above described effect can be observed. Sganarelle, the close servant and personal assistant of Don Juan is much more openly opposed to his master's action. Nevertheless according to his social role he is forced to assist his master in order to seduce the sceptical Dona Elvire:

DON JUAN: *Madame, voilà Sganarelle, qui sait pourquoi je suis parti.*

SGANARELLE: *Moi, Monsieur, je n'en sais rien, s'il vous plaît.*

DONA ELVIRE: *Hé bien, Sganarelle, parlez, il n'importe de quelle bouche j'entende ses raisons.*

DON JUAN: *Allons, parle donc à Madame.*

SGANARELLE: *Que voulez-vous que je dise?*

DONA ELVIRE: *Approchez, puisqu'on le veut ainsi, et me dites un peu les causes d'un départ si prompt.*

DON JUAN: *Tu ne répondras pas?*

SGANARELLE: *Je n'ai rien à répondre, vous vous moquez de votre serviteur.*

DON JUAN: *Veux-tu répondre, te dis-je?*

SGANARELLE: *Madame...*

Don Juan wants Sganarelle to vouch for him and to lie or to excuse his actions in front of Elvire. The master himself is out of imagination and forces his servant to answer the critical questions of the betrayed Dona Elvire. By openly showing the disbalance in social power and his discomfort Sganarelle succeeds in communication towards Elvire and towards the spectators of the play, while Don Juan is stripped of his disguise. The explicit revelation of the master's power and the servant's discomfort adds a new layer of meaning and makes it even more difficult to read and interpret the text using NLP or any other distant reading methods. Nevertheless, the hypothesis that this is a common phenomenon in 17th century European drama can be shown in completely different plays like Molière's *Don Juan* and Racine's *Phèdre*. In the latter *Phèdre's* servant Oenone claims her innocence by pointing out after *Phèdre's* suicide:

OENONE: *Et plaignant à la fois son trouble et vos alarmes,
J'ai servi malgré moi d'interprète à ses larmes.*

- The servant acts as **a philosopher and the author's voice**: The role of the fool or "gracioso" (Coquín) in Calderón's *El médico de su honra* is a little bit different from the usual servant who is mostly bound to one master. In the following example Coquín answers to the king with a longly explanation regarding his ability to adapt his identity to the master's (in this case the king):

REY: *¿Quién sois?*

COQUÍN: *¿Yo, señor?*

REY: *Vos.*

COQUÍN: *Yo*

(¡válgame el cielo!) soy quien

*vuestra Majestad quisiere
sin quitar y sin poner,
porque un hombre muy discreto
me dio por consejo ayer
no fuese quien en mi vida
vos no quisieseis; [...]*
[Act I; ll.711—740]

To be able to apply quantitative digital methods of NLP in these last three cases it seems rather unlikely to succeed on a purely distant reading level and at the large scale. The very distinction of the literary method used by several authors (in our example Spanish and French dramas) is the uncharacteristic use of language and the forced misunderstanding between the different figures. The fact that the very same figure (in our case the servant) can act in various roles and changes accordingly the language and style of the speech makes it difficult or probably impossible to find a common pattern for each character of the play or for a group of characters (e.g. servants and masters).

Clustering of the character representations

We compare the theoretical question of a distinction between the speech of various social classes (masters, servants) using statistical analysis of the speech of the respective classes. The main idea is to use unsupervised clustering on the continuous vector representations of each character and comparing the results of the unsupervised clustering with the human-made definition of clusters (corresponding to the social classes).

We create a continuous representation (a fixed, real-valued vector) of each character based on their speech. From the available methods, we chose to compare representations based on stylometry and a TF-IDF-based approach.

TERM FREQUENCY–INVERSE DOCUMENT FREQUENCY REPRESENTATIONS

TF-IDF (Term frequency - inverse document frequency, Aizawa, 2003) is a method used in information retrieval focused on creating document representations using the frequency of terms within a given document. The terms can range from single-word vocabulary terms to n-grams, or a combination of both. While the naive approach of counting the frequency of each vocabulary entry for each document (Footnote: in our case, we refer to the individual characters as documents) can help building representation of the document, it does not reflect the varying information value between the individual terms not only within each document but also in the context of the whole document collection. For example, the frequency of stopwords (e.g., and, or, ...) has a lesser value when finding similarities/differences between documents than for example using proper names, less frequent idioms, etc.. This is mainly due to the former being present in most documents within a collection while also being quite frequent most of the time. TF-IDF tries to counter this by not only counting the frequencies of terms within the individual documents but also favouring terms that are less common across the whole collection, i.e. that are present only in a small number of documents.

As a first step, TF-IDF representations of the characters were extracted based on their respective n-gram vocabulary. Based on the TF-IDF representations an unsupervised clustering of the characters was performed and the resulting clusters were compared with the human-defined character classes,

leading to either confirmation or rejection of hypothesis that a specific character group (e.g. @royal, @servants) is characterised by a distinct speech. Furthermore, before the end of the SSHOC project (April 2022) we perform the comparison using different TF-IDF characteristics - besides raw n-grams, we also compare n-grams of POS or syntactic labels to show whether there are distinct patterns in the sentence structure within a specific character groups. For the POS extraction and POS analysis, we use the UDPipe analysis tool.

[UDPipe](#) (Straka, 2018) is a trainable pipeline for tokenization, sentence segmentation, tagging, morphology, lemmatization and dependency parsing of [CoNLL-U](#) files. It is language-agnostic and can be trained given annotated data in the [CoNLL-U](#) format, fulfilling the [Universal Dependencies v2 specifications](#). It was developed and is currently maintained at the [Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics](#) at Charles University in Prague. The [Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics](#) hosts the [LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ](#) research infrastructure node, which in turn hosts the 24/7 running services based on UDPipe, which can be freely used over the internet.

Trained models are provided for nearly all UD treebanks. UDPipe is also available as a binary for Linux/Windows/OS X, as a library for C++, Python, Perl, Java, C#. Third-party R CRAN package also exists. UDPipe is a free software distributed under the Mozilla Public License 2.0 and the linguistic models are free for non-commercial use and distributed under the CC BY-NC-SA license, although for some models the original data used to create the model may impose additional licensing conditions. UDPipe is versioned using Semantic Versioning. Figure 17 shows an example of a sentence annotation, visualized using [TrEd](#) tree editor.

Figure 17. A visualisation of an example UDPipe output.

UDPipe has been trained and validated on mostly modern-era corpora within Universal Dependencies datasets. Thus, the application of the available models to out-of-domain corpora from a specific era (e.g. 16th, 17th century drama) can result in a decrease in accuracy. For this reason we performed a small scale manual evaluation on a portion of the available data to estimate the model accuracy when applied to the drama corpora in questions.

Table 5 shows UDPipe accuracy reported on the official UDPipe website and the accuracy measured on the drama corpora. We report both lemmatization and part-of-speech (POS) tagging accuracy after the tokenization by the UDPipe tokenization module. For Spanish and French, the drama in-domain performance is very similar to the general domain accuracy, although the reported in-domain accuracy might be a bit overestimated since only a limited sample of the data was used for validation. For English, the in-domain performance drops significantly, although the output produced by UDPipe is still usable for the purposes of our analysis. Due to a lack of training resources, we decided to avoid experiments focused on fine-tuning the English model for the drama domain.

Following the preprocessing by UDPipe, each file is processed by the clustering scripts. For each drama, we extract a separate “collection” of utterances assigned to the respective drama characters and create a TF-IDF vector representation of the character’s speech. We try different approaches to creating TF-IDF vectors, e.g. based on single tokens only, or using n-gram counts of various span. Afterwards, we apply unsupervised clustering on the TF-IDF representations of the drama characters

For clustering, we use the implementation in a Scikit-learn²⁰ Python library. We set the number of target clusters similar to the number of manually predefined character classes. We use ward-linkage (aiming at creating clusters with the lowest internal variance) agglomerative clustering algorithm to generate the character clusters. We experimented with other linkage types (single, complete, average), however, these often resulted in a “degenerated” clustering, creating only a single large cluster and merging it with the unclustered documents one-by-one in each clustering step.

Figure 17 shows an example of the visualisation after applying principal component analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the vector representations of the output clusters for the combination of the dramas Pedro Calderón de la Barca: *El médico de su honra* (The Surgeon of his Honour) and *La dama duende* (The Phantom Lady). Figure 18 (left) shows the results of clustering based only on the single-word (i.e., 1-gram) vocabulary, Figure 18 (right) shows the results when combining 1-, 2-, 3- and 4-gram (referred to as 1to4-gram) vocabularies.

In order to be able to validate the results of the NLP approach with the close reading approach, we needed to manually annotate the different social groups (masters and servants) for both Spanish plays (see table below).

Title	Masters	Servants
El médico de su honra	dongutierre, reydonpedro Infantedonenrique, donarias, dondiego,	coquin, jacinta, teodora, soldados, musica, ines, viejo, ludovico

²⁰ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/index.html>

Title	Masters	Servants
	donamenciadeacuna, dongutierre, leonor	
La dama duende	donaangela, don-luis, don-juan, don-manuel, donabeatriz	clara, cosme, rodrigo, isabel,

The 1-gram clustering resulted in the following two clusters (characters are represented in a format of “<name-of-play-simplified>_<character-name>”). Blue color represents characters that we consider “masters”, red color represents the “servants”:

- cluster-0: medico_teodora, dama_clara, medico_soldados, medico_musica, medico_ines, medico_viejo
- cluster-1: dama_cosme, dama_donaangela, medico_dongutierre, dama_rodrigo, medico_ludovico, medico_infantedonenrique, medico_reydonpedro, dama_don-luis, dama_isabel, dama_don-juan, medico_donarias, medico_leonor, dama_don-manuel, medico_coquin, medico_jacinta, dama_donabeatriz, medico_donamenciadeacuna, medico_dondiego

The 1to4-gram clustering resulted in the following two clusters (characters are represented in a format of “<name-of-play>_<character-name>”):

- cluster-0: medico_teodora, dama_clara, medico_soldados, medico_musica, dama_rodrigo, medico_ludovico, medico_ines, medico_viejo, medico_dondiego
- cluster-1: dama_cosme, dama_donaangela, medico_dongutierre, medico_infantedonenrique, medico_reydonpedro, dama_don-luis, dama_isabel, dama_don-juan, medico_donarias, medico_leonor, dama_don-manuel, medico_coquin, medico_jacinta, dama_donabeatriz, medico_donamenciadeacuna

Figure 18. (left and right): Clustering of the characters from chosen plays by Pedro Calderón de la Barca. Left: character representations created using only 1-grams. Right: character representations created using a combination of 1-, 2-, 3- and 4-grams. Ward-linkage was used to create clusters.

Based on the results, most of the “master” characters end up in the same clusters. While this can support the hypothesis of the class distinction based on the speech we must also address the fact that many of the “servant” characters also end up in the same clusters as the “masters”.

To gain a more fine-grained insight into the cluster creation, we also repeated the clustering process using hierarchical clustering and stylometry. Figure 18 shows the dendrograms illustrating the clustering process of the 1-gram representations (left) and 1to4-gram representations (right).

Even though the dendrograms based on TF-IDF representations give more insight into the clustering process, the results in Figure 19 do not show any clear distinction between the “master” and “servant” characters. There are smaller homogenous clusters emerging, however, it is impossible to find a reasonable cut-off level (resulting in more than two clusters) that results in clear “master”-only “servant”-only clusters.

Figure 19. Dendrograms showing the process of cluster merging. Complete-linkage clustering method was used. The TF-IDF representations were normalized to length of 1 and cosine distance was used as a distance metric. Left: based on 1-grams only. Right: using 1to4-grams

For comparison, we also performed clustering based on stylometry metrics. Stylometry is one of the most common methods in Computational Literary Studies and relies on the comparison of words (or other defined features) and their frequency in single text and in a collection of text. The matrix of frequencies is represented in a high dimensional vector space. Each text becomes a high dimensional vector (each word or other feature like n-grams of words or POS elements has its own position and dimension in the vector). The distance between the vectors is calculated using a distance measure “Delta” (cf. Evert et al. 2017). There are many different measures (Deltas) like Burrow’s, Manhattan’s or Eder’s. For literary texts the Würzburg Cosine Delta has proved to be the most effective (cf. Jannidis et al. 2015). With the stylo package for R (Eder et al. 2013) we can set different parameters for the stylometric analysis.

Figure 20. Dendrogram of Cluster analysis using stylo package for R²¹. Parameters set on 250 Most Frequent words, no culling, Würzburg Delta

As the length of the single character speech is very different from character to character, the stylistic difference which is detected here can also be caused accidentally by the text length. The lower arm at the bottom of the dendrogram represents only servants - but if you look closely into these speeches, they are all rather short. While the upper arm of the dendrogram shows only speeches of the “dama duende” play we also don’t know if these similarities are caused by the style and different choice of vocabulary in the different plays. In general stylometry does not consider the topics or content words but the most frequent words (stopwords) as important indicators for distinctiveness.

²¹ Stylometry with R: a package for computational text analysis. R Journal 8(1): 107-121.
<https://journal.r-project.org/archive/2016/RJ-2016-007/index.htm>

Lemmatization	English	Spanish	French
general domain	0.958	0.994	0.977
drama domain	0.786	1.000	0.999
POS tagging	English	Spanish	French
general domain	0.963	0.991	0.972
drama domain	0.749	0.965	0.979

Table 5. General-domain and In-domain (drama) evaluation of UDPipe accuracy.

3. Conclusion

This deliverable reports on the use of TDM for three SSH use cases, and provides pointers to the outcome of this work, available via external code repositories, such as Google CoLab and GitHub, while referenced in the workflows on the SSH Open Marketplace, and as a service listed in the EOSC Portal:

- CBAs agreements processing and analysis: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/iRDSS0>
- Verbal Aggression analysis: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/verbal-aggression-analyser-va-analyser> (EOSC Portal information will be harvested by SSH Open Marketplace)
- Drama corpora processing: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/DMJlZG>

Three use cases showed how linguistic analysis performed in a pipeline of tools can support the SSH researchers in their work, allowing them to process data on the large scale, run comparative studies across the languages, and share both the findings, and the gained experience working with the tools with the scientific community in the environment of SSH Open Marketplace.

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